

The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on the Virtual Work Performance in Exponential Organizations

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This research revolved around how emotional intelligence impacts on virtual work performance in exponential organizations. By knowing how technological development has affected traditional organizations to turn into exponential organizations and their work performance.

The sub-objectives:

- I. How do employees' emotional intelligence, and their relationships within the organization affect work performance.
- II. Does the exponential thinking have an impact on the performance of the virtual work within the exponential organization.
- III. Does the creative and innovative employees, have an exponential thinking.

This study used quantitative approaches. It is conducted using a survey methodology and as a primary source of data. The population consisted of (13) exponential organization in Jordan, and a sample of (440) manager and employee has been chosen. The results of the study indicated that there are no differences in the opinions of the study sample individuals about the Impact of emotional intelligence on virtual work performance in exponential organizations, as it was found that there is no difference in the opinions of males and females, also it was found that there is no difference in opinions according to position. It was also found that there is a positive correlation relationship with statistical significance between emotional intelligence and virtual work performance.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, Exponential organization, Virtual work, Work performance.

I. Introduction

The world now is in an ongoing process because of technology development, more innovation, from linear thinking to exponential thinking, and globalization. Most organizations have multiple facilities that are connected to each other because of technology and the development of the telecommunication structure.

With technology development, the competition increases between organizations to be better, faster, and cheaper. To achieve all of these, organizations must consider the performance of employees inside the organizations. When the employees are creative and have the ability to understand and manage their emotions in a positive way, it will lead to an efficient virtual work performance. We argue that people with higher levels of individual virtual competence will perform their work activities better than people with lower levels of individual virtual competence, consistent with the effect of individual competence in other contexts and given our continuum view of virtual work (i.e., all work is more or less virtual, not all work is either virtual or not), and given our continuum view of virtual work (i.e., all work is more or less virtual, not all work is either virtual or not). (Wang, Y., & Haggerty, N. (2011).

In recent years, psychology science has been increasingly interested in emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is said to be one of the most important characteristics that determines life success and psychological well-being (Bar-On R, 2001; Goleman D, 1995). We must consider the KSA intellectual human capital (knowledge, skills, and abilities), to be

more innovative and creative as an exponential organization. The knowledge, skills, and abilities are particularly relevant in virtual teams—meaning that such KSAOs are more relevant for individual team members’ and the team’s success in virtual than in traditional teamwork. The purpose of it, we asked experienced members of either virtual or traditional teams to assess the relevance of KSAOs for their type of teamwork (Krumm, S., Kanthak, J., Hartmann, K., & Hertel, G. (2016).

Individuals can access the information they need to perform their job and coordinate work activities in locations other than the traditional office, such as from a home office, satellite work center, client office, airport, or hotel, thanks to rapid advances in mobile computing power and high-speed internet access. Virtual workers typically spend a portion of their time in various places and communicate with one another by email, phone, and web-based databases (Golden, T. D., & Veiga, J. F. (2008)).

II. The Massive Transformative Purpose

The massive transformative purpose (MTA) is the soul of any organization, and the purpose of the organization is to be better, faster, and cheaper. It is the reason for change and being better, and it is the reason to improve the workplace inside the organization and increase productivity, collaboration, working virtually more effectively, creativity, and thinking outside of the box. This is the way exponential organization works. With the mta, any organization can differentiate themselves from other competitors by attracting top-talented employees and managers and differentiating themselves from other competitors with new ideas.

Exponential organizations share ten elements or attributes, as well as a Massive Transforming Purpose (MTP), which is a very high aspirational purpose or intention. The qualities are divided into two categories: SCALE and IDEAS are two terms that refer to the brain's creative (right) and rational (left) hemispheres (Díaz-Piloneta, M., Ortega-Fernández, et...2021).

Figure (1) Díaz-Piloneta, M., Ortega-Fernández, et...2021

III. Research problem

This research will revolve around how emotional intelligence impacts on virtual work performance in exponential organizations. By knowing how technological development has affected traditional organizations to turn into exponential organizations and their work performance, and how employees from more than one country connected within one virtual network to know the performance of work outcomes, Is the intelligent development, capabilities, and skills of employees and managers a reason for an organization to be an exponential organization that builds and structures itself on creativity and innovation? All of these are questions to be answered in this research.

With the development of technology, several considerations must be taken such as:

- Is work performance improved?

- How did social relations become within the organization?
- Is there an impact of technological development on employees and their practical and virtual performance?
- Does emotional intelligence affect virtual work performance?
- Is the performance of employees within the exponential organization better than the traditional ones?

Because of the varied ideas and viewpoints that individuals bring to the group assignment, we expect that conflict will arise in the teams during the problem-solving exercise. Emotions arise from feelings of threat to individual or collective interests as a result of these discrepancies (Borisoff & Victor, 1998).

Research objectives

The main objective of this research is to find out how emotional intelligence affects the performance of employees in the exponential organizations.

The sub-objectives:

- IV. How do employees' feelings, dealings with others, and their relationships within the organization affect work performance.
- V. Does the exponential thinking have an impact on the performance of the virtual work within the exponential organization.
- VI. Does the creative and innovative employees, have an exponential thinking.
- VII. Did the Technological development has an important factor in increasing communication and collaboration between employees in many countries, thereby improving productivity and work performance.
- VIII. To help humans and companies to thinking out of the box (from linear thinking to exponential thinking).
- IX. To increase the KSA capital.

The variety of claims made about emotional intelligence is quite broad. Emotional intelligence, for example, is said to be...

- 80 percent of work performance and life success are determined by this factor (Goleman, 1995).
- is inextricably tied to advancement in one's profession, Individuals who are better leaders as a result of this process, People become self-starters and self-motivated as a result of this (Goleman, 1998).
- contributes to better teamwork (Druskatt & Wolff, 2001).
- leads to better decisions (Jordan, Ashkanasy & Hartel, 2002).
- is a valuable framework for dealing with a wide range of behavioral issues (Gillis, 2004).

IV. Research hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is relationship between emotional intelligence and employee's virtual work performance.

Hypothesis 2: There is a statistically significant relationship to the responses of the study sample individuals about the Impact of emotional Intelligence on virtual work performance in exponential organizations due to demographic variables (gender, position)

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relation between employees creativity, innovation and exponential thinking in exponential organizations.

V. Research significance

In this research, we are going to discuss and explain the linkage between emotional intelligence and the performance of work teams virtually and within the firm environment. The findings of my research highlights how much controlling our emotions will reflect on our work performance, it will discuss whether employee's emotional intelligence help the employee taking control over his job and excel in his field or it represent an obstacle for him.

The results of the study will be of great benefit to the following:

Employers and large firms: Data given will help the employers and most firms dealing with their subordinates and how to orient their emotional intelligence in the most effective way to the benefit of the company and how to formulate teams whether virtually or within the firm's boundaries and for whom to put as a team leader and whom to assign as a virtual team member or as a normal work team member.

Academic and Students: Besides the benefit of the information provided for employers it also can be relied on when conducting more specialized studies for the linkage between emotional intelligence and employee's performance.

Governments: When governments decide to switch the methodology conducted about how they perform their work, this research will help them through their transition into more flexible structure that support the approach of emotional intelligence performance.

VI. Literature review

Emotional intelligence (EI) is the capacity to perceive, use, understand, manage, and handle emotions is most commonly defined as the ability to recognize, utilize, understand, manage, and handle emotions. People with high emotional intelligence are able to notice their own and others' emotions, utilize emotional information to drive their thoughts and conduct, distinguish between different feelings and name them properly, and alter emotions to fit their surroundings, and people with high EI have a greater mental health, leadership skills, better job performance, self-motivated, self-awareness, abilities, knowledge, and many of skills. EI being able to inspire oneself and persevere in the face of adversity; controlling urge and delaying gratification; regulating one's feelings and keeping distress from obstructing one's capacity to think; empathizing and hoping' (Goleman, 1996). by focused on a certain set of emotional processing skills (perceiving and identifying feelings in self/others, emotional integration and facilitation of thinking, emotional understanding; thinking about feelings, emotional management (Salovey, P. and Mayer, J. (1990).

Intelligence and emotions have been studied as parts of mental operations as well as physiological and behavioral response patterns in different situations (Smith, K. B., Profetto-McGrath, J., & Cummings, G. G. (2009), emotional intelligence is a set of personality traits and abilities that predict emotional and social adaptation within any situations (Bar-On (2005).

Individual performance is a crucial variable in work and organizational psychology, as evidenced by the extensive use of individual performance measures in single research and meta-analyses. Individual performance is largely regarded as a dependent variable, which makes perfect sense from a practical standpoint: companies aim to improve and maximize individual performance (Sonnentag, S., & Frese, M. (2002).

Virtual teams may interact using a variety of computer-mediated communication mechanisms, including teleconferencing, instant messaging, and e-mail ((Bell & Kozlowski, 2002). Team outputs, which include objective (e.g., profit; task-related performance) and subjective (e.g., collective efficacy, team viability) measures of team effectiveness outcomes, are proposed to be driven by team processes, which include open communication, coordination, and conflict management, all aspects of high quality communication ((Gladstein, 1984; Hackman, 1987; Marks et al., 2001; Mathieu et al., 2008).

"A temporary, flexible arrangement of scattered components provided by many companies and connected together using information technology" is how the virtual organization is defined (Robey, Boudreau and Storey (1998).

Exponential organization in the last five years, the world has witnessed the emergence of Exponential Organization, a concept initially introduced in 2008 at Singularity University with the goal of assisting a person or a corporation in positively impacting the lives of a billion people, it's the newest incarnation of human culture and industry, are reshaping commerce and other elements of contemporary life at a breakneck speed that will rapidly leave the old world of "linear organizations" in the dust (Ismail, S. (2014).

We're increasingly experiencing the macroeconomic impact of this new information-based paradigm, which is causing the world's metabolism to heat up. for example, the cheapest 3D printers currently cost less than \$100, implying that most of us will be able to purchase 3D printers to build toys, cutlery, tools, and fittings within the next five years or so. This "printing revolution's" ramifications are nearly incomprehensible (Ismail, S. (2014).

Because emotional intelligence is linked to team performance in face-to-face teams, it's crucial to see if the same holds true for virtual teams, which are one of the most frequent means of professional communication in the twenty-first century (Cascio, 2003).

Let's take a look at exponential organizations. To their working environment, it's like an organic environment (adaptive, collaborative, information sharing, and horizontal structure). As the employees inside the exponential organization are intrapreneurs, let's think deeply. If the employees are intrapreneurs, they must have a virtual team to share information between them and have multiple new ideas that will improve the organization. Also, the virtual work performance will improve. So, to be a successful, innovative organization and have a competitive advantage, you must have the dimensions of emotional intelligence (self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management). In virtual teams, emotional intelligence has the potential to be a key driver of effective communication and consequent effectiveness outcomes (e.g., team performance, team members' attitudes) (Pitts, V. E., Wright, N. A., & Harkabus, L. C. (2012).

Today we have a paradigm shift from linear thinking to exponential thinking, such as Nokia and Kodak they didn't go to exponential thinking as Apple, Samsung, and Facebook...etc, exponential thinking based on miles and snow strategies to be a prospector where there is an opportunity to exploit it and where there are strengths to use it. Also, we have a paradigm shift in technology, emotional intelligence, work performance. Instead of owning and safeguarding assets, exponential companies make use of plentiful external resources. Salim Ismail and his co-researchers investigated over 100 firms that have expanded exponentially in the previous five years and discovered common characteristics among all exponential businesses (Subramanian, K. P., & Balanagarajan, K. (2018).

Table (1): Comparing Linear Thinking vs Exponential Thinking

Differences	Linear thinking paradigm	Exponential thinking or paradigm
Type of miles and snow strategy	Defender or Reactor	prospector
structure	vertical	horizontal
goals	Realistic or logic goals	Ambitious goals
Decision making	Centralized	Decentralized
Work performance	Stable (focus on efficiency)	Ongoing and increased (focus on learning and growth)
Emotional intelligence	Based on rational and logical	Empathy, ability to understand others (SKA intellectual capital)
Assets	Tangible Assets	Intangible Assets
Growth	Incremental	Exponential
Reality	Objective Reality	Disruptive innovation

Source: prepared by Authors

Despite the fact that sustainability is a vital pillar for businesses, few really manage to put in place steps that lead to a long-term business strategy. Organizational transformation toward exponential development, on the other hand, is a critical effort that is difficult to implement without following monitoring (Díaz-Piloneta, M., Ortega-Fernández, et...2021).

Because of the tangible results it has produced in the management of organizations at various administrative levels, emotional intelligence has received a lot of attention. As a result, emotional intelligence is a relatively new concept with a wide range of implications for solving issues and making good judgments (Refat Alfaouri, Esra' Tahat 2020).

VII. Research Methodology

This study will use quantitative approaches. It is conducted using a survey methodology and as a primary source of data, in addition previous research related to this research will be the reference for secondary data.

The survey and is cross-sectional because the data were collected at one point in time. Likert scale is used in the surveys in typical five-level Likert items, strongly disagree, disagree, Undecided, agree, and strongly agree

A variety of statistical techniques were utilized in this research. Means, standard deviations, t-tests, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were utilized in this study.

Study Population and Sample:

The study population consisted of (13) exponential organizations in Jordan, and study sample of (440) individuals (managers and employees) was determined, a set of demographic factors were selected for the respondents, such as (gender, position, and company founding). This is in order to clarify some facts related to this category of society, and its members have been distributed according to their personal characteristics, as follows:

Table (2) Frequency and percent for demographic variable (N.440)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent %
Gender	Male	230	52.3%
	Female	210	47.7%
Position	Employee	330	75.0%
	Employer	110	25.0%
The company founding	Less than 15 years	7	54%
	15 – 20 years	4	31%
	More than 20 years	2	15%

Table (2) shows the following:

The results indicated that the majority of the study sample (52.3%) were males, while the lowest percentage was for females, reaching (47.7%) of the study sample, which indicates that the answers to the study questions will be greater from the point of males. While the percentage of employee was the highest, reaching (75%), while the percentage of Employer was the lowest, reaching (25%) of the study sample

The previous table shows that the study sample was distributed according to the company founding, as the percentage of (15 - 20 years) reached (31%), while the percentage of (Less than 15 years) amounted to (54%) of the study sample.

Study tool

The research questionnaire was prepared electronically to achieve the objectives of the study to obtain field survey information, and the questionnaire consisted of main parts as follows:

- The first section: It contains 5 questions related to the demographic variables of the study sample, which are: (gender, position, the company founding).

- The second section: It included 2 dimensions related to Impact of Emotional Intelligence on virtual work performance in exponential organizations:
- (8) Questions about emotional intelligence
- (8) Questions about virtual work performance

Questionnaire scale

The five-Likert scale was adopted to determine the level of answers in the study tool, giving each of its paragraphs one score out of its five scores (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree) and are represented numerically (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) respectively, and the following scale was adopted to explain the estimates of the study sample for each item and its field:

- Low score is from 1.00 - 2.33
- Medium score from 2.34 to 3.67
- High score is from 3.68 to 5.00

Descriptive statistical results

This study attempted to answer the questions that represented its problem and the hypotheses on which it was based. All arithmetic averages and standard deviations were extracted for the questions related to their variables, and the following tables show the responses of the study sample members to the questions specific to each axis of the study, which were as follows:

Table (3) Arithmetic means and standard deviations (Emotional intelligence) (N.440)

#	Questions	Mean	Standard deviation	Degree
1	I prefer sharing my feelings among groups	4.06	0.847	High
2	I prefer sharing my feelings in a private sessions with a specialists	4.18	0.833	High
3	Have you ever faced an emotional issue that affects your performance	3.87	0.848	High
4	Are you concerned about work environment and how much it means to you	3.60	0.795	Medium
5	Can you control your emotions	3.36	0.806	Medium
6	Do you have any bad past experiences with your emotions	3.92	0.935	High
7	Do you think that it is possible to separate your feelings from your work environment	3.95	0.845	High
8	Do you think you can control your emotions	3.66	0.991	Medium
	Total	3.80	0.856	High

Table (3) shows that the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample individuals regarding the emotional intelligence were high with an arithmetic average (3.80), where the table indicates that individuals prefer sharing their feelings in a private sessions with a specialists, and this question came first with an arithmetic mean (4.18). And in the last place was the question that stipulated that individuals can control emotions, with an arithmetic mean (3.36).

Table (4) Arithmetic means and standard deviations (Work performance) (N.440)

#	Questions	Mean	Standard deviation	Degree
1	Does the company working virtually	3.72	0.784	High
2	Does the company having Intelligence Teams	3.42	0.728	Medium
3	The degree to which your firm uses technology	3.55	0.902	Medium
4	What you give for the communications among the organisation	3.92	0.843	High
5	Prefer working virtually	4.29	0.882	High
6	Prefer working with teams	4.19	0.871	High
7	Satisfied with working virtually during pandemic (COVID-19)	3.62	0.731	Medium
8	Do you aware of your abilities and limitations	4.01	0.708	High
	Total	3.75	0.878	High

Table (4) shows that the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample individuals regarding the virtual work performance were high with an arithmetic average (3.75), where the table indicates that individuals prefer working virtually with an arithmetic mean (4.29). And in the last place was the question that stipulated that the company having Intelligence teams, with an average of (3.42).

Correlation coefficient

Table (5) Pearson Correlation Coefficient

Variables	Emotional intelligence	Virtual work performance
Emotional intelligence	1	
Virtual work performance	0.777**	1

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The statistical data in Table (5) indicate that the correlation coefficient between emotional intelligence and virtual work performance is significant at the level of significance (0.01). This indicates a positive correlation between variables. Moreover, from the previous analysis we can conclude that for most of the employees whom they have creative and innovative characteristics, they show tendency towards exponential thinking, and this leads to reinforcement of building exponential organizations. And, therefore, it has a great influence on their virtual work performance.

Test hypotheses of the study

H1: There is positive relationship between emotional Intelligence and virtual work performance

Table (6) Linear Regression

Variables	R	F-test	R ²	T-test
Emotional intelligence	0.777	67.335	0.184	8.206

Dependent variable: Virtual work performance

Table (6) shows the existence of a statistically significant correlation relationship at a level of 0.01, which indicates the existence of a correlation between the emotional Intelligence and virtual work performance, as the correlation coefficient was (0.777), which is statistically indicative of the existence of a positive correlation.

H2: There is a statistically significant relationship to the responses of the study sample individuals about the Impact of emotional Intelligence on virtual work performance in exponential organizations due to demographic variables (gender, position)

Table (7) One-Way ANOVA (Gender)

Variables	Male		Female		F	Sig.
	Mean	Sd.	Mean	Sd.		
Emotional intelligence	3.95	0.869	3.99	0.814	5.177	0.024
Virtual work performance	3.87	0.900	3.84	0.820	5.329	0.022

It is evident from Table (7) regarding the opinions of the study sample individuals according to the difference in gender that there are no differences in the opinions of the individuals, where the value of F and its significance at the level of 0.05 indicates the existence of no difference in opinions in all the variables, because the significance is less than the level of significance 0.05.

Table (8) One-Way ANOVA (Position)

Variables	Employee		Employer		F	Sig.
	Mean	Sd.	Mean	Sd.		
Emotional intelligence	4.01	0.798	3.88	0.811	4.002	0.001
Virtual work performance	3.93	0.809	3.85	0.902	5.658	0.032

It is evident from Table (8) regarding the opinions of the study sample individuals according to the difference in position that there are no differences in the opinions of the individuals, where the value of F and its significance at the level of 0.05 indicates the existence of no difference in opinions between managers and their employees, because the significance is less than the level of significance 0.05.

VIII. Discussion

The study aimed to identify the Impact of emotional intelligence on virtual work performance in exponential organizations. This part of the study includes discussing the results in light of the study questions and hypotheses to reach conclusions and recommendations.

The results of the study proved that the variables affecting exponential organizations that were included in the study (emotional intelligence, virtual work performance) were high and positive, as emotional intelligence came to occupy the highest arithmetic average of (3.80) and a standard deviation (0.856) this indicates the presence of interest in emotional intelligence in exponential organizations, also virtual work performance with an arithmetic mean of (3.75) and a standard deviation of (0.878), which indicates that the level of virtual work performance was high in exponential organizations.

The results of the study indicated that there are no differences in the opinions of the study sample individuals about the impact of emotional intelligence on virtual work performance in exponential organizations, as it was found that there is no difference in the opinions of males and females, also it was found that there is no difference in opinions according to position. It was also found that there is a positive correlation relationship with statistical significance between emotional intelligence and virtual work performance, as the correlation coefficient reached (0.777), which indicates the existence of a positive relationship.

Moreover, the traits of employees that relates to creativity and innovation has a positive effect on the employee exponential thinking. And, therefore, it has a great influence on their virtual work performance.

IX. Recommendations

This study recommends the need to pay attention to the concept of emotional intelligence and work to raise its level among employees, and pay attention to developing communication skills among employees in order to develop virtual work performance by offering communication skills courses. While setting organizational goals and policies that are flexible and easy, this study also recommends conducting future studies on larger samples in order to generalize the results.

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